

Ride 2Rail

D3.4 TRAVEL COMPANION ENHANCEMENTS

This project has received funding from the Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 881825

Project Acronym	RIDE2RAIL
Starting date	01/12/2019
Duration (in months)	36
Deliverable number	D3.4
Call Identifier	S2R-OC-IP4-01-2019
GRANT Agreement no	881825
Due date of the Deliverable	31/05/2022
Actual submission date	08/07/2022
Responsible/Author	OLTIS Group
Dissemination level	PU
Work package	WP3
Main editor	Petra Juránková
Reviewer(s)	Nicola Bassi (FIT), Ludovico Boratto (EUT)
Status of document (draft/issued)	issued

Reviewed: yes

CONSORTIUM OF PARTNERS

PARTNER	COUNTRY
UNION INTERNATIONALE DES TRANSPORTS PUBLICS (UITP)	Belgium
FIT CONSULTING	Italy
OLTIS GROUP	Czech Republic
FSTECH	Italy
CEFRIEL	Italy
CERTH	Greece
EURNEX	Germany
EURECAT	Spain
POLIMI	Italy
UNIVERSITY OF NEWCASTLE UPON TYNE	United Kingdom
UNIFE	Belgium
UIC	France
UNIZA	Slovakia
ATTIKO METRO	Greece
INLECOM	Greece
FV-Helsinki	Finland
METROPOLIA	Finland

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Revision	Date	Description
0.1	23/03/2022	First draft of structure and chapters
0.2	28/06/2022	Internal review of contributions
0.3	29/06/2022	Final internal review of the deliverable

REPORT CONTRIBUTORS

Name	Beneficiary Name	Short	Details of contribution
Petra Juránková	OLT		Main editor
Adriana Pálková	OLT		Table of content, introduction, conclusion
Viktor Patras	OLT		Sections 4.3
Cristian Consonni	EUT		Table of content
Luca Piras	EUT		Sections 4.1, 5.2
Rohit Kumar	EUT		Sections 4.1.3, 4.2, 4.2.1
Ľuboš Buzna	UNIZA		Sections 4.1.1, 4.1.2, 5.1
Milan Straka	UNIZA		Sections 4.1.1, 4.1.2, 5.1
Yannick Cornet	UNIZA		Sections 4.1.1, 4.1.2, 5.1
Tatiana Kováčiková	UNIZA		Sections 4.1.1, 4.1.2, 5.1
Nicola Bassi	FIT		Section 4.2
Matteo Giovanni Rossi	POLIMI		Section 4.1.4, 5.2

DISCLAIMER

The information in this document is provided “as is”, and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The content of this document reflects only the author’s view – the Joint Undertaking is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. The users use the information at their sole risk and liability.

The content of this report does not reflect the official opinion of the Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking (S2R JU). Responsibility for the information and views expressed in the report lies entirely with the author(s).

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Executive summary.....	7
2. Background.....	9
3. Objective.....	10
4. Development of Travel Companion Enhancements.....	11
4.1. Offer Enhancer and Ranker	11
4.1.1. Feature Enricher.....	12
4.1.2. Data Provider	12
4.1.3. OC core.....	21
4.1.4. THOR.....	23
4.1.5. OER core	24
4.2. Driver Companion.....	26
4.3. Deployment Infrastructure.....	27
5. Integration of R2R components	29
5.1. Integration with the Agreement Ledger	29
5.1.1. Calculation of incentives	29
5.1.2. Authentication with Agreement Ledger end-point.....	30
5.1.3. Implementation	30
5.1.4. Usage	32
5.1.5. Limitations and remarks	35
5.2. Integration with the Shift2Rail Ecosystem.....	35
5.2.1. Integration timeline.....	36
6. Conclusion.....	37
7. References.....	38
8. Appendix.....	39

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 - Overview of the architecture of the system.....11

Figure 2 - Class diagram of the Data Provider module.....15

Figure 3 - Illustration of how the Driver Companion works27

Figure 4 - Class diagram of the Incentive Provider module.....30

Figure 5 - Integration timeline within the project overall GANTT 36

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 - Incentives supported by the Incentive Provider module 29

Table 2 - Contact points for the integration process of R2R components..... 36

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the Travel Companion enhancements developed within WP3 in the RIDE2RAIL project. RIDE2RAIL project (H2020-Shift2Rail-881825) has the overall objective of creating an innovative framework for intelligent multimodal mobility by facilitating the efficient combination of flexible and crowdsourced transport services, such as ridesharing, with scheduled transport. This framework is integrated natively into existing collective and on-demand transport services, connecting, and reinforcing the mobility offers with ridesharing services, especially in rural and low-demand areas. The goal of R2R is to facilitate access to high-capacity services (rail, bus, and other public transport services) thanks to easy-to-use multimodal and integrated travel planning, booking, ticketing, and payment features. The R2R framework integrates real-time and diverse information about rail, public transport, and shared mobility in a social ecosystem.

This deliverable describes the results of the Task 3.4 Travel Companion enhancements when the existing Travel Companion was extended and enhanced by components developed within WP3. We report here the description of the task for clarity.

This task had two objectives:

1. to extend and enhance the existing Travel Companion solutions in the IP4 ecosystem;
2. to provide a way for drivers to offer ride-sharing offers.

The first task integrated the algorithms and modules developed in the previous tasks to extend and enhance the existing Travel Companion solution, such as those developed in the previous Shift2Rail IP4 projects COHESIVE and My-TRAC. This task provides the Travel Companion capabilities of user journeys when they offer shared rides. The second task developed the Driver Companion, a standalone application to allow drivers to add real rides, to be inserted into the Crowd-Based TSP, fully compliant with the IP4 ecosystem travel offer modality. It also provides tracking capabilities of shared rides and incentivisation mechanisms for passengers using the Travel Companion to become drivers, thus enriching IP4 travel offers. This app allows drivers to offer single rides that the Crowd-Based TSP collects charged for sending them to the IP4 Shopping Orchestrator; such rides are handled as any other IP4 travel offer, including acceptance by default like for other TSP rides. The Driver Companion was developed by leveraging and reusing the codebase developed in the context of the SocialCar project. Each feature implemented in the Driver Companion will be tested and validated in WP4.

ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

CbTSP	Crowd-based Transport Service Provider
CW	Cloud Wallet
H2020	Horizon 2020
IP4	Innovation Programme 4
OC	Open Call
OER	Offer Enhancer and Ranker
S2R JU	Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking
THOR	The Hybrid Offer Ranker
TSP	Travel Service Provider
WP	Work Package

2. BACKGROUND

The present document constitutes the Deliverable D3.4 “Travel Companion enhancements” in the framework of the WP3 “Development of enhanced Travel Companion and Ride-sharing TSP” and describes what has been developed within Task 3.4 of Ride2Rail project (S2R-OC-IP4-01-2019)

3. OBJECTIVE

This document has been prepared to provide description of the activities in the context of the Task 3.4 “Travel Companion enhancements”.

The general goal of this deliverable is to provide relevant and detailed information about the components developed within the WP3. These components enhance the Travel Companion, and it adds many additional features and advantages to the end users. The WP3 developed the components and modules, through which the Travel Companion is enhanced. These modules are as follow:

- Offer Enhancer and Ranker – through the joint contribution of a series of developed submodules, the rich characterization of the offers is provided to users. This component also ranks the offers in the most suitable order, according to their preferences. These enhancements are ensured by set of microservices, that interact with each other. Each of submodules are described in this deliverable in detail;
- Driver Companion – standalone application which enables to share rides for drivers. Through this component, the public transport is becoming more flexible and accessible.

The deliverable also describes the interaction and integration of developed components with the S2R ecosystem.

4. DEVELOPMENT OF TRAVEL COMPANION ENHANCEMENTS

This section provides the technical details of the implementation of the Offer Enhancer and Ranker and Driver Companion. The workflow of the system is illustrated in Figure 1

. The system has been designed as a set of microservices to be deployed as Docker containers, that interact with each other through HTTP requests and share a common Redis-cache, containing the trip data.

Figure 1 - Overview of the architecture of the system

4.1. Offer Enhancer and Ranker

The Offer Enhancer and Ranker has the objective of obtaining a rich characterization of the offers included in a trip request, so as to rank them in the most suitable order according to the preferences of the user who issued the request. This is achieved through the joint contribution of a series of submodules, which will be described in detail in the next sections:

- The Feature Enricher associates each offer to the city where the trip will take place, by decoding its geographical coordinates;
- The Data Provider retrieves the information about the user profile and preferences;
- The Offer Categorizer computes a series of descriptors that characterize each offer along dimensions such as quickness, comfort, environmental friendliness, etc.;
- The THOR component consists of a machine learning model that is fed with the features coming from the mentioned modules and computes the optimal ranking of the offers to be presented to the user;
- The flow of the execution and the interactions between components is managed by the Offer Enhancer and Ranker core, which is in charge of extracting the initial data, sending the requests over HTTPS protocols, handling the errors and writing to log.

4.1.1. Feature Enricher

Section 4.6 of D3.1, introduces the architecture of Offer Categorizer and the way how individual Feature Collectors interact with other components in order to compute offer categories. Individual Feature Collectors are detailed in Section 5 of D3.1. When implementing Data Provider module, a need arose to translate geographical coordinates (latitude, longitude) to the corresponding city names. For this purpose, the set of Feature Collectors developed in T3.1 was extended by adding “geo-location-fc” Feature Collector.

Geo-location-fc

The “geolocation-fc” is a module of the Ride2Rail Offer Enhancer and Ranker responsible for translation of geographical coordinates to city or location names. Such names are later used by the THOR module as features to estimate the probability that a user will select a given travel offer.

The geo-location-fc module is implemented as a Flask app. The code is available on the GitHub Ride2Rail repository: <https://github.com/Ride2Rail/geolocation-fc> (please note that some Ride2Rail repositories are private and can be accessed only after receiving access rights from Mr. Cristian Consonni). The translation of the coordinates is done by the external service that is based on the OpenStreetMap and is called Nominatim. It is possible to install own instance of the Nominatim service or use publicly available one. The instance of the Nominatim to be used is defined in the configuration file geolocation-fc.conf, section nominatim_options:

```
[nominatim_options]
```

```
domain = default
```

```
user = default
```

When setting default values, the publicly available Nominatim service is used. Similarly, to Feature Collectors, the connection to the Offer-cache needs to be also configured. The geo-location-fc service can be requested by calling the method *compute* implemented in the Python script *geolocation-fc.py*. The request should contain as parameters *request_id*

(identifier of the mobility request) and `geo_attributes` (a list of attribute names to be translated).

An example of the POST request:

```
curl -X POST http://127.0.0.1:5015/compute -d '{"request_id": "123x", "geo_attributes":
["start_point", "end_point", "via_locations"]}' \
-H "Content-Type: application/json"
```

As a response, one of the following outputs is obtained:

- If everything runs fine, the geolocation-fc API returns JSON containing city names and 200 response code;
- If there was used a wrong input data (e.g., invalid value of an attribute), the geolocation-fc API returns JSON containing the problem description and 400 response code;
- If the writing or reading the Offer-cache fails, API returns 500 response code.

4.1.2. Data Provider

The Data Provider is a Flask app that ensures extraction of data required by the Ranker from the Cloud Wallet (CW) and Offer-cache. Only data needed for the ranking of Travel Offer Items are extracted. Before sending requests to the CW, it is required to obtain a communication token from the IP4 Login end-point. The code is available on the GitHub Ride2Rail repository: <https://github.com/Ride2Rail/data-provider> (please note that some Ride2Rail repositories are private and can be accessed only after receiving access rights from Mr. Cristian Consonni).

Authentication with IP4 Login end-point

This step requires registration of the service at the IP4 Login end-point. Afterwards, the Data Provider module is assigned `serviceId` and `secret`. Valid values need to be defined in the configuration file [data_provider_api.conf](#):

```
[api_auth_service]
secret = <ASSIGNED SECRET>
serviceId = <ASSIGNED SERVICE_ID>
```

Alternatively, registration at the IP4 Login end-point can be associated with a user. In such a case, the user is assigned a `password` associated with the `email` address provided by the user. Valid values need to be defined in the configuration file [data_provider_api.conf](#):

```
[api_auth_user]
email = <EMAIL ADDRESS>
password = <PASSWORD>
```

Authentication token

For the communication with CW, a valid communication token must be issued by the IP4 Login end-point. The request returning communication token has several parameters characterizing the issuer of the request. Values of these parameters need to be defined in the configuration file [data_provider_api.conf](#):


```
[api_headers]
device_id = 0
device_type = A
latitude = 0
longitude = 0
locale_id = 0
provider_id = s2r-client
service_name = 0
user_agent = curl/7.78.0
```

The meaning of the parameters is the following:

- **device_id** (string): unique identifier of the device issuing the request;
- **device_type** (string): type of the device issuing the request. A for Android, I for iOS and W for Web. Available values: A, I, W;
- **latitude** (number): latitude where the request was issued from;
- **longitude** (number): longitude where the request was issued from;
- **locale_id** (string): locale identifier of the device issuing the request;
- **service_name** (string): name of the service being requested. In this case, anonymous;
- **user_agent** (string): information about the application issuing the request.

The URL of the Login end-point can be specified by setting the parameter **auth_url** in the configuration file [data_provider_api.conf](#). For the mocked Login end-point, this can be done in Section **mockup_api**:

```
[mockup_api]
auth_url = <URL ADDRESS>
```

For the Login end-point in the production this can be done in Section **prod_api**:

```
[prod_api]
auth_url = <URL ADDRESS>
```

The authentication is implemented by classes `AuthReqHeader` and `AuthTokenObtainer` located in the script [request_support.py](#).

User preferences

User preferences are requested from the CW-Preferences end-point. The request must contain a valid authentication token obtained from the IP4 Login end-point and *user_id*. The module makes the authentication requests automatically while taking the required inputs from the configuration file (see Section Authentication with IP4 Login end-point) and also takes care of the update of the token when its validity expires.

The CW-Preference API and the scheme followed by the returned JSON file are documented at the Swagger page: [Preference API](#). If a request to the CW-Preferences end-point succeeds, the structured JSON is obtained. The information in the JSON is organized by using the following tags: *category*, *subcategory*, *elements*, and *preferences*. The Data Provider module extracts the values associated with the preferences.

The class ProfileManager, located in the script [data_request_manager.py](#), implements the request for the user preferences data. The class PreferenceReqDataExtractor, located in the script [request_data_extractor.py](#), implements the extraction and formatting of user preference data.

To see an example of the output containing user preferences, please refer to Section [Usage](#).

User profile

User profile information is requested from the CW-Profile end-point. The request must contain a valid authentication token obtained from the IP4 Login end-point and *user_id*. The authentication is the same as for the CW-Preferences end-point. The module makes the authentication requests automatically while taking the required inputs from the configuration file (see Section Authentication) and also takes care of the update of the token when its validity expires.

The CW-Preference API and the scheme followed by the returned JSON are documented at the Swagger page: [Profile API](#). If the request to the CW-Profile end-point succeeds, the structured JSON is obtained. The information in the JSON file is wrapped by the tag *data* that contains the user profile information organized by using the following tags: *name*, *email*, *externalProviderUserId*, *userData*, *personInfo*, *metadata*, *address*, *contacts*, *termsComditions*, *preferences*, *fullAddresses*, *profiles*, *profileDefault*.

Currently, the CW-Profile end-point is not mocked. For the CW-Profile end-point in the production mode, the URL can be set in Section **prod_api** in the configuration file [data_provider_api.conf](#) by defining the parameter **profile_url**.

```
[prod_api]
profile_url = <URL ADDRESS>
```

The class ProfileManager, located in the script [data_request_manager.py](#), implements the request for the user profile data. The class ProfileReqDataExtractor, located in the script [request_data_extractor.py](#), implements the extraction and formatting of profile data.

Offer-cache

Data related to the travel information request are obtained from the [Offer-cache](#). The Offer-cache implements a Redis in memory key-value database storing XML files.

Implementation

The Data Provider module is implemented by classes presented in Figure 2. The code is organized in several Python scripts as indicated in the figure by the dashed rectangles.

Figure 2 – Class diagram of the Data Provider module

Script [data_provider api.py](#)

This is the main script running the Flask API. The function `return_data()` implements the response to a HTTP GET requests with `user_id` as a parameter. The script implements the main algorithm followed by the Data Provider. After receiving a request with the `request_id`, the Data Provider extracts the `user_ID` from the Offer-cache. This `user_id` is used to request CW-Preference and CW-Profile end-points. Obtained data is complemented by search options retrieved from the Offer-cache and outputted.

Script [request_support.py](#)

The script implements several classes described below to handle the communication via APIs.

Class AuthReqHeader

Class to read the headers used for the authentication API from the configuration file.

Class AuthToken

Class to obtain the authentication token from the IP4 Login end-point. The function `obtain_token()` returns the authentication token. If something goes wrong, the object of class `MyResponse` containing error information is returned. The obtaining of authentication token is always handled exclusively by a single request. If more requests are processed in parallel, the other requests wait till the token is obtained. This is ensured via binary semaphores with timeout.

Class RequestObtainer

Class to obtain the user preferences from the CW end-points. The values of parameters that are used to form the request are read from the configuration file. The object *AuthToken* executes the authentication. The user preferences data request is performed by calling the function *load_request()*. The function returns a dictionary containing the response from user preferences and user profile APIs with keys *preferences* and *profile* respectively. If something goes wrong, the error is logged with the support class *MyResponse*.

Class MyResponse

Class to create and to write to the log file the error messages. If something fails, it returns the HTTP code 400 and writes the error code and description to the log file. Otherwise, the HTTP code 200 is returned. The error code and description are logged when creating the object of this class, and the HTTP code is set when calling the function *get_response()*. The function *get_response()* returns the tuple: (JSON, HTTP code).

Script [request_data_extractor.py](#)

Class MyJSONdataExtractor

It is an abstract class used as a superclass for the data extractor classes.

Class RequestDataExtractor

Some of the user preferences are described by string variables. To comply with the values of strings that the *THOR* module recognizes as a description of user preferences, this class translates the string values received from CW-Preferences end-point in the JSON file to string values supported by the *THOR* module. The function *extract_json()* defines two dictionaries *translate_prefs_dict* and *translate_valKeys_dict* used in the translation process.

Class ProfileReqDataExtractor

The data received from the CW-Profile end-point are in JSON format. The class *ProfileReqDataExtractor* ensures extraction of the attributes required by the *THOR* module.

Script [data_request_manager.py](#)

Class CWDataManager

This is the abstract class used as a superclass to classes managing communication with CW.

Class PreferenceManager

The class manages communication with CW-Preference end-point, and it handles errors and manages the request result processing.

Class ProfileManager

The class manages communication with CW-Profile end-point, and it handles errors and manages the request result processing.

Usage

Local development (debug on)

Before launching the service on the localhost, make sure that in the configuration file [data_provider_api.conf](#), section *cache*, the *host* is set to value *localhost*. This is required for establishing the connection to the [Offer-cache](#):

```
[cache]
host = localhost
port = 6379
```


The Data Provider service can be launched from the terminal locally by running the script [data_provider_api.py](#):

```
python data_provider_api.py
2022-02-18 07:36:44 - data_provider_api - INFO - config loaded successfully
* Running on http://127.0.0.1:5010/ (Press CTRL+C to quit)
* Serving Flask app 'data_provider_api' (lazy loading)
* Environment: development
* Debug mode: on
```

The Data Provider was configured to run by default on the port 5010.

Docker environment

Before launching the service on the localhost, make sure that in the configuration file [data_provider_api.conf](#), section *cache*, the *host* is set to value *cache*. This is required for establishing the connection to the [Offer-cache](#):

```
[cache]
host = cache
port = 6379
```

The Data Provider service can be launched on Docker from the terminal in two steps:

1. Go to the *data-provider* directory and build the Docker image

```
$ docker-compose build
```

2. Run the Docker container

```
docker-compose up
Creating data-provider ... done
Attaching to data-provider
data-provider | * Serving Flask app 'data_provider_api.py' (lazy loading)
data-provider | * Environment: production
data-provider | WARNING: This is a development server. Do not use it in a production deployment.
data-provider | Use a production WSGI server instead.
data-provider | * Debug mode: off
data-provider | 2022-02-18 07:23:32 - data_provider_api - INFO - config loaded successfully
data-provider | * Running on all addresses.
data-provider | WARNING: This is a development server. Do not use it in a production deployment.
data-provider | * Running on http://172.19.0.4:5000/ (Press CTRL+C to quit)
```

Requesting Data Provider service

Example of the curl command to receive a JSON with user data associated with `<request_id>`:

```
curl -X GET "http://127.0.0.1:5010/?request_id=<request_id>"
```

Example of the returned JSON file:

```
{
  "request_id": "826b25a5-dcde-4f34-9650-173e917c333b",
  "trip_request": {
    "cycling_dist_to_stop": "10",
    "cycling_speed": "fast",
    "driving_speed": "slow",
    "expected_duration": "2",
    "leg_information": {
```



```
"36e5c5b9-b434-40c4-8017-9ec79578813a": {
  "num_legs": 6,
  "transportation_mode": [
    "walk",
    "cycle",
    "walk",
    "bus",
    "others-drive-car",
    "walk"
  ]
},
"5c08395c-7efc-4418-a2dc-c2794e7120f6": {
  "num_legs": 6,
  "transportation_mode": [
    "walk",
    "cycle",
    "walk",
    "bus",
    "others-drive-car",
    "walk"
  ]
},
"731d2c82-e158-4d87-8cd6-df9bbcc647e6": {
  "num_legs": 5,
  "transportation_mode": [
    "walk",
    "cycle",
    "walk",
    "bus",
    "walk"
  ]
},
"c421d948-8741-4b33-8797-3871ec8b3b7f": {
  "num_legs": 3,
  "transportation_mode": [
    "walk",
    "bus",
    "walk"
  ]
},
"ef9012a8-918b-4e20-a724-rs1": {
  "num_legs": 6,
  "transportation_mode": [
    "walk",
    "cycle",
    "walk",
    "bus",
    "others-drive-car",
    "walk"
  ]
}
},
"max_transfers": "2",
"traveller_id": "b343adc2-a2fd-4f52-9969-2cf220b46daf",
"user_id": "b343adc2-a2fd-4f52-9969-2cf220b46daf",
```



```
"via": [
  "Madrid",
  "Toledo",
  "Barcelona"
],
"walking_dist_to_stop": "4",
"walking_speed": "medium"
},
"user_preferences": {
  "Class": {
    "Business": "0.0",
    "Economy": "0.0",
    "First class": "0.0"
  },
  "Loyalty/Reduction/Payment card": {
    "Cartafreccia": "0.0",
    "FlyingBlue": "0.0",
    "Golden Card": "0.0",
    "Grand Voyageur": "0.0"
  },
  "PRM type": {
    "Older person": "0.0",
    "Persons porting a carrycots": "0.0",
    "Persons with blindness or visual impairments": "0.0",
    "Persons with deafness or auditory impairments": "0.0",
    "Persons with impairments in their members / users of temporary
wheelchair": "0.0",
    "Pregnant women": "0.0",
    "Wheelchair users in mainstreaming seat": "0.0"
  },
  "Payment Card": {
    "Apple Wallet": "0.0",
    "Google Wallet": "0.0",
    "Mastercard": "0.0",
    "Paypal": "0.0",
    "Visa": "0.0"
  },
  "Preferred carrier": {
    "AirFrance": "0.0",
    "FlixBus": "0.0",
    "Iberia": "0.0",
    "KLM": "0.0",
    "RegioJet": "0.0",
    "Renfe": "0.0",
    "SNFC": "0.0",
    "TMB": "0.0",
    "Trenitalia": "0.0",
    "VBB": "0.0"
  },
  "Preferred means of transportation": {
    "Airline": "1.0",
    "Bike Sharing": "1.0",
    "Bus": "1.0",
    "Cable Way": "1.0",
    "Car Sharing": "1.0",
```

```
"Coach": "1.0",
"Funicular": "1.0",
"Intercity": "1.0",
"Metro": "1.0",
"Other": "1.0",
"Park": "1.0",
"Ship": "1.0",
"Taxi": "1.0",
"Toll": "1.0",
"Train": "1.0",
"Tram": "1.0",
"Trolley Bus": "1.0",
"Urban": "1.0"
},
"Refund Type": {
  "Automatic refund": "0.0",
  "Manual refund": "1.0"
},
"Seat": {
  "Aisle": "0.0",
  "Large": "0.0",
  "Window": "0.0"
}
},
"user_profile": {
  "birth": "2021-11-24",
  "city": "Hannover",
  "country": "DE",
  "profileDefault": "business",
  "profiles": [
    "basic",
    "business",
    "family",
    "leisure"
  ]
}
}
```

Response

The Data Provider returns a tuple (JSON, HTTP status code). If the request was processed without a major error the JSON contains the data and has the following structure:

```
{
  "request_id": "<request_id>",
  "user_preferences": "<user_preferences>",
  "user_profile": "<user_profile>",
  "trip_request": "<trip_request>"
}
```

The following responses are possible:

- JSON, 200: if the request was successfully processed;

- JSON, 200: if the request was only partially processed (e.g., there is no account associated with given *user_id* in the CW, the CW is not working, or the *request_id* is missing in the Offer-cache), the corresponding missing data are set to *null* in JSON;
- {'error':'Data provider error. User id was not extracted'}, 500: if an exception is risen when retrieving *user_id* from the Offer-cache;
- {'error':'Unexpected RequestException'}, 500: if a RequestException occurred during the execution of a request;
- {'error':'Internal server error'}, 500: if an unexpected error occurred during the execution of a request.

Error messages are logged to the file [error.log](#). This file is meant to be used only in the connection with local copies of the Data Provider. For this reason, this file is included in the *.gitignore* file and thus its content is not uploaded from local copies onto the GitHub.

Limitations and remarks

- JSON containing the user preferences is compatible with the version 1.0.0 of Swagger API specifications [Preference API](#);
- Only the string values characterizing the preferences that are defined in the translation dictionaries (implemented by the class RequestDataExtractor) are supported;
- Data Provider is not doing any advanced analyses of the JSON contents (e.g. it is not checked whether the information about all expected user preferences is provided).

4.1.3. OC core

The Offer Categorizer core is the module that is in charge of the management of the whole workflow of the Offer Categorizer, which, through the contribution of a series of modules called Feature Collectors, computes a set of determinant factors that evaluate the trip offers along dimensions such as quickness, comfort, environmental friendliness, etc. In particular, the Offer Categorizer core is responsible for setting up the connections between the other components, combining their input and output, aggregating the determinant factors for each category, carrying out the categorization of the offers and handling the errors that might occur at any point in the computation.

From a general perspective, the steps performed by the Offer Categorizer core can be summarized as follows:

1. The Offer Categorizer core sends a request to all Feature Collectors;
2. The Feature Collectors retrieve the determinant factors and store them into the cache;
3. When all Feature Collectors respond, the Offer Categorizer core aggregates the determinant factors for each category (according to the algorithm described in Section 5.5 of D3.1);
4. The Offer Categorizer core assigns category scores to each offer and writes the data into the cache.

Requests are carried out through HTTP protocol, via POST. It is noteworthy that, in step 3, the requests are sent to the different Feature Collectors in an asynchronous fashion, so as to limit the overall latency to the computation time of the slowest Feature Collector.

Usage

The service is deployed as a Docker container and can be launched with the `docker-compose up` command, which brings it up together with all the Feature Collectors. Please

note that, in order to be able to execute the application, the user first needs to upload the TRIAS data and initialize the TRIAS-extractor.

The response is a JSON structured on two levels: the first-level keys correspond to the travel offer ids, while the second-level keys are the names of the categories, each associated to a score normalized between 0 and 1.

```
{  
  "dd19551d-7e9e-45b1-9442-3482e5d92055": {  
    "cheap": 0.6852,  
    "comfortable": 0.209,  
    "door-to-door": 0.0,  
    "environmentally_friendly": 0.0,  
    "healthy": 0.0,  
    "multitasking": 0,  
    "panoramic": 0.0,  
    "quick": 0.9043999999999999,  
    "reliable": 0.5376,  
    "short": 0.0764  
  },  
  "fd796c85-0afe-44ae-86f1-2c2f0c70f444": {  
    "cheap": 0.162,  
    "comfortable": 0.1493,  
    "door-to-door": 0.0,  
    "environmentally_friendly": 1.0,  
    "healthy": 0.0,  
    "multitasking": 0.0,  
    "panoramic": 0.0,  
    "quick": 0.3942,  
    "reliable": 0.1884,  
    "short": 0.9236  
  }  
}
```

4.1.4. THOR

THOR (The Hybrid Offer Ranker) is the component that is in charge of handling the preference models of users. In particular, it is able, on one hand, to learn user preference models from travel offers selected by users in the past and, on the other hand, to use these models to rank new travel offers based on the likelihood that the user, given their preferences, will select them.

The underlying principles and mechanisms of THOR have been described in Deliverable D3.2 – “Source code of Algorithms for optimal synchronisation of shared-mobility and mass transit”. This section provides an overview of the implementation of THOR.

The implementation of THOR has been realized as a set of functions in the Python language and is available from the RIDE2RAIL GitHub repository.¹ It offers 4 core functions (which are defined in the `tasks.py` file):

- `make_classifier_for_user` – takes as input the information related to “old” users (i.e., users who are associated with a large enough number of past selected travel offers, hence for whom there is enough training data) and, for each of the users, creates a custom preference model (i.e., a “classifier”);
- `cluster_users` – takes as input the profiles of a set of “old” users, and groups them into clusters of users with similar characteristics (from the profile similarity point of view); these clusters are later used to create so-called “cluster preference models”, which capture the learned preferences of the group of users, and which are later used as the initial preference models for “cold users” (i.e., users for whom there is not enough data to train a user-specific model);
- `new_user_cluster_pred` – takes as input a set of new users (for which there is no data, hence also not enough data to train a user-specific preference model) and assigns each of them to one of the clusters identified through function `cluster_users`;
- `sort_offers` – which takes as input a list of offers to be ranked, and the user(s) for which the offers must be ranked and uses the preference model associated with the user to classify each offer and determine, for each offer, the likelihood that the user will buy it. Then, the function sorts the offers according to the likelihood that the user will buy them, from the most likely, to the least likely.

Note that function `sort_offers` uses a different preference model depending on whether the user is “old” or “cold”. Indeed, if the user is “cold”, the preference model associated with the user will be the one of the user cluster to which the user belongs; if the user is “old”, instead, the preference model associated with the user will be the one trained used only user-specific data (hence, it is will specifically tailored to the behaviour of the user). The details of the approach can be found in Deliverable D3.2.

The information regarding user profiles, the offers selected by the users in the past, and the offers to be ranked are loaded from the Offer-cache, which is used to store and load the classifier models as well.

¹ https://github.com/Ride2Rail/Learner_Ranker/tree/main/THOR_V2

4.1.5. OER core

The Offer Enhancer and Ranker core manages the workflows of the whole system, from the extraction of the TRIAS data containing the trip request, up to the ranking of the offers. Similarly, to what the Offer Categorizer core does for the Offer Categorizer, the OER core sets up the connection between the different components, makes sure that the dependencies between them are respected, handles the errors, writes into the log.

The system pipeline can be summarized as follows:

- The Offer Enhancer and Ranker core sends a request to the TRIAS-extractor (described in Section 5.4.1 of D3.1), which extracts the trip request data and stores it into the cache;
- The Offer Enhancer and Ranker core sends a request to the Feature Enhancer, which assigns a city name to offers and updates the cache;
- The Offer Enhancer and Ranker core sends asynchronous requests to Offer Categorizer core, Data Provider and Incentive Provider, each of which writes the newly obtained data into the cache;
- The Offer Enhancer and Ranker core sends a request to THOR, which returns the offer ranking.

Usage

The service is deployed as a Docker container and can be launched with the docker-compose up command, which brings it up together with the all the rest of components, including the TRIAS-extractor, the Offer-cache, the Offer Categorizer (Offer Categorizer core and Feature Collectors), the Data Provider and the Incentive Provider.

The response is a JSON with the following structure:

```
{
  "result": [
    {
      "blockchain-incentives": {
        "10discount": false,
        "20discount": false,
        "trainSeatUpgrade": false
      },
      "categories": {
        "cheap": 0.6852,
        "comfortable": 0.209,
        "door-to-door": 0.0,
        "environmentally_friendly": 0.0,
        "healthy": 0.0,

```



```
"multitasking": 0,  
"panoramic": 0.0,  
"quick": 0.9043999999999999,  
"reliable": 0.5376,  
"short": 0.0764  
},  
"offer_id": "dd19551d-7e9e-45b1-9442-3482e5d92055",  
"ranking": {  
  "rank": 1,  
  "score": 0.856291038154392  
}  
},  
{  
  "blockchain-incentives": {  
    "10discount": false,  
    "20discount": false,  
    "trainSeatUpgrade": false  
  },  
  "categories": {  
    "cheap": 0.162,  
    "comfortable": 0.1493,  
    "door-to-door": 0.0,  
    "environmentally_friendly": 1.0,  
    "healthy": 0.0,  
    "multitasking": 0.0,  
    "panoramic": 0.0,  
    "quick": 0.3942,  
    "reliable": 0.1884,  
    "short": 0.9236  
  },  
}
```



```
"offer_id": "fd796c85-0afe-44ae-86f1-2c2f0c70f444",  
"ranking": {  
  "rank": 0,  
  "score": 1.0  
}  
}  
]  
}
```

4.2. Driver Companion

The Driver Companion is an Android app that serves drivers. Drivers use the Driver Companion to create rides. These ride requests are sent to the CbTSP through REST APIs. When a request is sent, it's kept in the database of CbTSP. Then, it sends back the journey plan. The plan has the detailed driving journey turn-by-turn from origin to destination. The Driver Companion displays the journey on Maps to the user.

On the other side, CbTSP might use this journey to offer lifts to interested travellers. When a traveller is offered this journey, Driver Companion is informed that a traveller has accepted the ride and will join the driver at a start and end locations.

The Driver Companion shows start and end journeys per travellers so the driver can travel and stop at the start destination of the first traveller. The Driver Companion also shows the destination in which the traveller(s) leaves at. That is displayed on Maps and communicated using notifications to help the driver navigate their journey and serve their own travellers.

The Driver Companion uses the latest Android development APIs to collect and share driver's location at the start and during the journey while adhering to GDPR rules. Some of the screenshots of the app is illustrated.

The Driver Companion has a built-in tutorial to showcase its functionality to each demo tester. This eradicates any learning curve for a smooth adoption and usage of the app during the R2R demos.

Figure 3 – Illustration of how the Driver Companion works

Figure 3 shows how the drivers log in, greet, and inform of their location sharing, asked to select a demo site and then gets their journey shared and displayed on the app. In addition to how to change settings on the app.

4.3. Deployment Infrastructure

The Server has been temporarily provided by OLTIS Group for the purposes of the Ride2Rail project and its physical location is in Olomouc (Czech Republic).

The server is publicly reachable without any need for a VPN connection. Server address is <https://ride2rail.oltisgroup.cz>, the CbTSP is reachable using <https://ride2rail.oltisgroup.cz/cbtsp>. HTTPS support has been enabled for the server using an SSL certificate provided by “Let’s Encrypt”.

HW configuration:

- RAM: 16 GB;
- CPU: Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2665 0 @ 2.40GHz, 4 core;

- HDD: 40 GiB system, 400 GiB data;
- HDD partitions: swap - 4 GiB, / (root) - 40 GiB (include /home), /data - 400 GiB.

SW configuration:

- Operating system: CentOS Linux release 7.9.2009 (Core);
- http server: Apache/2.4.6 (CentOS) built Nov 10 2021 14:26:31;
- Docker Client: Docker Engine - Community : Version: 20.10.12 : API, version: 1.41 : Built: Mon Dec 13 11:45:41 2021;
- Docker Server: Docker Engine - Community : Version: 20.10.12 : API, version: 1.41 (minimum version 1.12) : Built: Mon Dec 13 11:44:05 2021.

5. INTEGRATION OF R2R COMPONENTS

5.1. Integration with the Agreement Ledger

The integration with the Agreement Ledger is ensured by the R2R module Incentive Provider. The Incentive Provider module is implemented as a Flask app. The code is available on the GitHub Ride2Rail repository: <https://github.com/Ride2Rail/incentive-provider> (please note that some R2R repositories are private and can be accessed only after receiving access rights from Mr. Cristian Consonni).

The Incentive Provider pre-evaluates the eligibility to receive travel incentives. The incentives are associated with travel offers. The current version supports the incentives listed in Table 1.

Table 1 – Incentives supported by the Incentive Provider module

INCENTIVE	DESCRIPTION
10%Discount	The incentive is associated with a travel offer item if at least one ride-sharing leg is included in any travel offer item.
20%Discount	The incentive is associated with a travel offer item if the offered item contains at least one ride-sharing leg and the passenger completed at least three ride-shares. The counter of completed ride-shares is set to zero after allocating the incentive.
FreeSeat	The incentive is associated with a travel offer if at least one other passenger booked at least one of the ride-shares included in the travel offer item.

5.1.1. Calculation of incentives

Incentive 10%Discount

For a given *request_id*, the corresponding list of travel offer items and the transport modes associated with legs are obtained from the [Offer-cache](#). Based on this data, the presence of ride-sharing legs is analysed in the method *checkFulfilled()* of the class *RideSharingInvolved* implemented in the script [rules.py](#).

Incentive 20%Discount

For a given *request_id*, the corresponding list of travel offer items, Traveller ID and the transport modes associated with legs are obtained from the [Offer-cache](#). If an offer item contains a ride-sharing leg, Traveller ID is used to request the Agreement Ledger module to obtain information about the eligibility to receive 20%Discount incentive. Otherwise, it is concluded that offer item is not eligible for this incentive. The evaluation is implemented by the method *checkFulfilled()* of the class *ThreePreviousEpisodesRS* implemented in the script [rules.py](#).

Incentive FreeSeat

For a given *request_id*, the corresponding list of trip leg IDs and the corresponding transport modes are obtained from the [Offer-cache](#). If an offer item contains a ride-sharing leg, trip leg ID is used to request the Agreement Ledger module to obtain information about the eligibility to receive FreeSeat incentive, and it is outputted. Otherwise, it is concluded that offer item is not eligible for this incentive. The evaluation is implemented by the method `checkFulfilled()` of the class *TwoPassShared* implemented in the script [rules.py](#).

5.1.2. Authentication with Agreement Ledger end-point

This step requires registration of the service at the Agreement Ledger Login end-point. Afterwards, the Incentive Provider module is assigned a *secret*. Valid values need to be defined in the configuration file [incentive_provider_api.conf](#). The URL can be set in the section *agreement_ledger_api*:

```
[agreement_ledger_api]
auth_url = URL_OF_AUTHENTICATION_AGREEMENT_LEDGER_END_POINT
```

The *secret* can be set in the section *auth*:

```
[auth]
basic_secret = SECRET
```

5.1.3. Implementation

Incentive Provider module is implemented by Python scripts and classes that are presented in Figure 4. Reference source not found.

Figure 4 – Class diagram of the Incentive Provider module

Script [communicators.py](#)

The script implements Communicators. A Communicator is a class ensuring interaction with an external service.

Class Communicator

The class *Communicator* is an abstract class serving as a common predecessor for classes that implement communication with external services.

Class AgreementLedgerCommunicator

The class *AgreementLedgerCommunicator* ensures sending a request to the Agreement Ledger. It implements reading of URLs and of other parameters from the config file [incentive_provider_api.conf](#). Further, it creates an instance of the class *RequestObtainer* that ensures the execution of requests. The request is executed by the method *accessRuleData()*.

Class OfferCacheCommunicator

The class *OfferCacheCommunicator* ensures sending a request to the [Offer-cache](#). It reads the host address and port from the config file [incentive_provider_api.conf](#) and uses them to establish a connection with the Offer-cache. The request to obtain data from the Offer-cache is executed by calling the sequence of methods that are implemented by this class. By calling the method *accessRuleData()*, the request to get data from the Offer-cache is executed. Depending on the level of requested data, methods *read_data_from_offer_cache()* and *redis_request_level_item()* are called. The method *read_data_from_offer_cache()* ensures calling of the method *read_data_from_cache_wrapper()* from the package *r2r_offer_utils* that for a given *request_id* reads the required attribute values at the levels of offer item and trip leg. The method *redis_request_level_item()* reads the required values of attributes at the level of the mobility request.

Script [AL_requester.py](#)

The script implements classes ensuring interaction (authentication and sending of request) with Agreement Ledger.

Class AuthTokenObtainer

The class implements acquisition and renewal of the communication token from the Login end-point. The URL and headers need to be provided as parameters. If more requests simultaneously ask for an authentication token from Agreement Ledger API, only the first one is processed, and the others wait until the first one is served. This is implemented by the binary Semaphore mechanism.

Class RequestObtainer

The class executes requests to an External end-point. It reads the parameters of the Authentication end-point from the configuration file [incentive_provider_api.conf](#). It is expected that the class *AuthTokenObtainer* had ensured the acquisition of the communication token. The instances of *RequestObtainer* should possess a single instance of *AuthTokenObtainer* to allow token sharing. The method *load_request()* executes authentication and the request to the external service. The handling and logging of error situations is separated in the method *checkResponse()*.

Class MyResponse

The class wraps up the response received from methods that ensure communication with external services. In addition, it takes care of logging the errors. Sometimes an instance of the class is created solely for the error logging purposes.

Script [rules.py](#)

The script implements rules that pre-evaluate the eligibility of offer items to be assigned an incentive.

Class Rule

This class is a common predecessor of classes implementing rules. It is expected that every rule will be implemented by a class inherited from the class *Rule*. The pre-evaluation is implemented by the method *checkFulfilled()*.

Class TwoPassShared

The class pre-evaluates the eligibility to receive the *FreeSeat* incentive.

Class RideSharingInvolved

The class pre-evaluates the eligibility to receive the *10%Discount* incentive.

Class ThreePreviousEpisodesRS

The class pre-evaluates the eligibility to receive the *20%Discount* incentive.

Class Incentive

The class maintains the results of a rule evaluation for later use, e.g., for the consistency check or for the final output of results. An instance of the class *Incentive* is created for every offered item and every type of incentive.

Script [incentive_provider.py](#)

The script implements the upper layer of the Incentive Provider module. It takes care of the initialization of rules that are applied in the pre-evaluation process and the initialization of incentives. The script implements the way how the rules are applied and the consistency check that ensures that only mutually compatible incentives are returned for each offered item.

Class IncentiveProvider

The class *IncentiveProvider* implements the method *getEligibleIncentives()* that executes each rule on each offer item, and the method *consistencyCheck()* that evaluates constraints defining the mutual compatibility of incentives. Currently, to demonstrate this functionality, the incentives *10%Discount* and *20%Discount* are considered to be mutually incompatible and if rules assigned both these incentives to a single offer item, during the consistency check the eligibility for *10%Discount* is cancelled.

Class IncentiveProviderManager

The class *IncentiveProviderManager* ensures correct initialization of the Incentive Provider and implements the method *getIncentives()* that calls the methods implemented by the class *IncentiveProvider* to execute the pre-evaluation of incentive eligibility.

5.1.4. Usage

Local development (debug on)

Before launching the service on the localhost, make sure that in the configuration file [incentive_provider_api.conf](#), section *cache*, the *host* is set to value *localhost*. This is required to establish a connection to the [Offer-cache](#).

```
[cache]
host = localhost
port = 6379
```

The module Incentive Provider can be launched locally from the terminal by running the script "incentive_provider_api.py":


```
2022-01-17 11:29:45 - incentive_provider_api - INFO - config loaded successfully
* Serving Flask app 'incentive_provider_api' (lazy loading)
* Environment: development
* Debug mode: on
* Running on http://127.0.0.1:5011/ (Press CTRL+C to quit)
```

The Incentive Provider was configured to run by default on the port 5011.

Docker environment

Before launching the service on the Docker, make sure that in the configuration file [incentive_provider_api.conf](#), section *cache*, the *host* is set to value *cache*. This is required to establish a connection to the [Offer-cache](#).

```
[cache]
host = cache
port = 6379
```

1. Go to the incentive-provider directory and build the Docker image

```
$ docker-compose build
```

2. Run the Docker container

```
docker-compose up
```

```
Starting incentive-provider ... done
Attaching to incentive-provider
incentive-provider | * Serving Flask app 'incentive_provider_api.py' (lazy loading)
incentive-provider | * Environment: production
incentive-provider | WARNING: This is a development server. Do not use it in a production deployment.
incentive-provider | Use a production WSGI server instead.
incentive-provider | * Debug mode: off
incentive-provider | 2022-01-27 07:10:51 - incentive_provider_api - INFO - config loaded successfully
incentive-provider | * Running on all addresses.
incentive-provider | WARNING: This is a development server. Do not use it in a production deployment.
incentive-provider | * Running on http://172.18.0.4:5000/ (Press CTRL+C to quit)
```

Please note that the Incentive Provider container connects to the Docker network *trias-extractor_offer-enhancer-net*. to be able to communicate with other modules. Hence, this network must be established prior to running the Incentive Provider container. Such a network is created when the TRIAS-extractor module is launched in the Docker environment.

Requesting Incentive Provider

Example of the curl command to receive a JSON with information about the incentives associated with the travel offers included in the request, which is identified by `<request_id>`:

```
curl -X GET "http://127.0.0.1:5011/incentive_provider/?request_id=< request_id >"
```

Example of the returned JSON:

```
{
  "36e5c5b9-b434-40c4-8017-9ec79578813a": {
    "10discount": true,

```



```
        "trainSeatUpgrade": true,  
        "20discount": false  
    },  
    "ef9012a8-918b-4e20-a724-rs1": {  
        "10discount": true,  
        "trainSeatUpgrade": true,  
        "20discount": false  
    },  
    "731d2c82-e158-4d87-8cd6-df9bbcc647e6": {  
        "10discount": false,  
        "trainSeatUpgrade": false,  
        "20discount": false  
    },  
    "5c08395c-7efc-4418-a2dc-c2794e7120f6": {  
        "10discount": true,  
        "trainSeatUpgrade": true,  
        "20discount": false  
    },  
    "c421d948-8741-4b33-8797-3871ec8b3b7f": {  
        "10discount": false,  
        "trainSeatUpgrade": false,  
        "20discount": false  
    }  
}
```

Response

The Incentive Provider returns the JSON as exemplified in the Section Requesting Incentive Provider. If the request is successfully processed, the JSON contains for each travel offer a list of all incentives and the value "true" or "false" indicating the result of the incentive eligibility pre-evaluation.

For the correct functionality of the Incentive Provider the functional connection to the Offer-cache component is essential. So, if there is no information associated with the provided *request_id* in the Offer-cache or if the connection to the Offer-cache is not functional the Incentive Provider returns the following JSON together with the HTTP code 200:

```
"offers": {  
    "no_offer": {  
        "10discount": false,  
        "trainSeatUpgrade": false,  
        "20discount": false  
    }  
}, 660-1326-4b6b-bf00-132ec7e576de"  
* Closing connection 1  
(base)
```

In a case, if the authentication or a request to the Agreement Ledger fails, the eligibility to receive the corresponding incentives is set to "false" and the HTTP status code 200 is returned. The information about the experienced errors is reported to the standard output and logged to the file *error.log*.

Error responses

In some cases, HTTP code 500 can be returned:

- If there is no *request_id* provided in URL parameters;
- If an unexpected exception emerged when processing incentives;
- If the writing of the results to cache failed.

5.1.5. Limitations and remarks

The communication with the Agreement Ledger could become faster if requests are run in parallel. However, the preliminary experiments showed favourable response times of the Agreement Ledger, and thus there was no need to further optimise the code.

5.2. Integration with the Shift2Rail Ecosystem

The integration phase was planned with the following approach: each software component to be delivered would be assigned a contact point that would receive any questions related to any integration issues or bugs that would arise during the integration process. Each contact point would also have a backup to ensure that requests and inquiries would be handled smoothly even when the main contact point was not available.

Table 2 - Contact points for the integration process of R2R components

COMPONENT	REFEREN CE TASK	CONTACT POINTS
Offer Categorizer + Offer Matcher and Ranker	T3.1 + T3.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • main: Cristian Consonni (EUT), cristian.consonni@eurecat.org • backup: Luca Piras (EUT), luca.piras@eurecat.org
Crowd-based TSP	T3.3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • main: Diego Lisi (FSTECH), d.lisi@fstechtechnology.it • backup: Enrica Caiello (FSTECH), e.caiello@fstechtechnology.it
Trip tracking component	T3.3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • main: Alexander Nemirovskiy (POLIMI), alexander.nemirovskiy@polimi.it • backup: Matteo G. Rossi (POLIMI), matteo.rossi@polimi.it
Driver Companion	T3.4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • main: Mohamed Taher Alrefaie (FIT), mo@premio.ai • backup: Fabio Cartolano (FIT), cartolano@fitconsulting.it
Agreement Ledger	T3.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • main: Harris Niavis (INLECOM), harris.niavis@inlecomsystems.com • backup: Socrates Katsoulacos (INLECOM), socrates.katsoulacos@inlecomsystems.com
Infrastructure	T3.4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • main: Viktor Patras (OLT), patras@oltis.cz; Petra Juránková (OLT), jurankova@oltis.cz • backup: Petr Buchniček (OLT), petr.buchnicek@oltisgroup.cz

5.2.1. Integration timeline

Figure 5 - Integration timeline within the project overall GANTT

Figure 5 shows the integration timeline within the project GANTT. Months M28;-30 have been devoted to the integration.

6. CONCLUSION

In this deliverable, the results of the Task 3.4 (Travel Companion enhancements), in the context of WP3 of the RIDE2RAIL project have been described. The components have been designed and developed within the WP3 to ensure the enhancement of Travel Companion and to meet the goal of the project. Description of these components is included in the deliverable.

The Offer Enhancer and Ranker provides the rich characterization of the offers included in a trip request. The set of microservices have been developed, which are able to interact with each other. Offer Enhancer and Ranker consist of several submodules, which are described in this deliverable in more details. It ranks the offers in order according to the user preferences, which are obtained from the CW-Preferences end-point and also it computes and provides a set of determinant factors that evaluate the trip offers along dimensions such as quickness, comfort, environmental friendliness, etc. The whole workflow of the Offer-Categorizer is managed by Offer-Categorizer core. The Offer-Categorizer core is responsible for setting up the connection between the other components, combining their input and output, aggregating the determinant factors for each category, carrying out the categorization of the offers and handling the errors that might occur at any point in the computation. One of the project goals was to make the ride sharing as a complementary service to the public transport and for this reason the Driver Companion was developed. The Driver Companion is a standalone application through which drivers can share their rides. Through the Driver Companion the shared rides are perceived as an effective feeder for public transport. The Driver Companion has a lot of useful functionalities which make the ride-sharing efficient and more common.

The developed components have been deployed into the server provided by responsible partner (OLTIS Group), and the server's physical location is in Olomouc in the Czech Republic.

The developed components have been integrated within the Shift2Rail ecosystem. Due to this, the contact points (responsible partners) were determined for each component developed within the WP3. In the case if the main contact point is out of office, the backup persons were determined to ensure seamless and smoothly integration.

7. REFERENCES

RIDE2RAIL. (2021). *Deliverable 3.1 - Quantitative Estimate of Service Quality Factors*. Retrieved from: <https://ride2rail.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/RIDE2RAIL-D3.1-Quantitative-Estimate-of-Service-Quality-Factors.pdf>

RIDE2RAIL. (2021). *Deliverable 3.2 - Source Code of Algorithms for optimal Synchronization of Shared-mobility and Mass Transit*.

8. APPENDIX